

The CEDA Archive: Data, Services and Infrastructure

Kevin Marsh

Centre for Environmental
Data Archival (CEDA)

www.ceda.ac.uk

*with thanks to V. Bennett, P. Kershaw,
S. Donegan and the rest of the CEDA
Team*

What is CEDA?

- The Centre for Environmental Data Archival
- Includes BADC
- Serves the environmental science community through 4 data centres and involvement in a host of projects

www.ceda.ac.uk

The screenshot shows the website for the Centre for Environmental Data Archival. The header includes the logo and name of the Centre, along with the Science and Technology Facilities Council and Natural Environment Research Council. A search bar and navigation links are present. The main content area is titled 'Data Centres' and lists four data centres: British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC), NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC), The UK Solar System Data Centre, and IPCC Data Distribution Centre. Each entry includes a logo and a brief description of the centre's role and the data it manages. The footer contains copyright information and contact details.

CEDA home page: <http://www.ceda.ac.uk/>

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the CEDA home page. The browser's address bar shows www.ceda.ac.uk. The page header features the CEDA logo, the text "Centre for Environmental Data Archival", and the affiliations "SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL" and "NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL". There are links for "Contact Us" and "CEDA News", and a search bar. A navigation menu includes "About CEDA", "Data Centres", "Services", "Projects", "For Academics", "For Business", "Help", and "Contact Us". The main content area is divided into two columns: "Welcome to the Centre for Environmental Data Archival" and "CEDA News". The "Welcome" section contains introductory text about CEDA's mission and contact information. The "CEDA News" section lists recent news items, including "CMIP5 web-based processing tools launched under the CEDA WPS July 23, 2013, 4:42 p.m.", "2 Scientific Applications Developers posts at CEDA July 18, 2013, 3:37 p.m.", and "Data Extractor Service officially retired - CEDA WPS to replace it May 23, 2013, 9:56 p.m.". The footer includes logos for the "National Centre for Atmospheric Science" and the "National Centre for Earth Observation", along with copyright information: "Copyright © 2011 STFC | All Rights Reserved" and "Original design by 1234.info". A cookie notice is visible at the bottom of the page.

About CEDA

- Based at RAL, Oxford.
- One of several NERC Data Centres in the UK.
- Supports national/international projects funded by NERC, EU, UK Government, etc. and helps develop international standards (e.g. OGC)
- Promotes good data management practice.
- Help develop data policy for NERC, Data Management Plans.
- Provides dedicated user helpdesks/community support/ file format advice CF-Standard names for variables, etc.
- Supports data users and providers
- >200 datasets, >100 Million files, ~2Pb of data.
- Many datasets are available free for academic use.

- **NERC's view is that data is an asset and needs to be properly managed**
- Just finding data can be a challenge....!

NERC Data Catalogue Service (DCS)

- CEDA supports the NERC DCS to allow users to easily find and access the data they need across all of the Data Centres – ARSF in this case.

NERC Data Catalogue Service (DCS)

http://data-search.nerc.ac.uk/

Search for data

Home About the DCS Search for data Your comments About NERC science Contact us Privacy and cookies

Data Catalogue Service (DCS)

The Earth changes constantly and understanding the past plays an important role in the prediction of future change. The data collected by NERC provide a unique and irreplaceable environmental record.

The NERC Data Centres are responsible, in accordance with the NERC Data Policy, for preserving NERC's data for the long term and for providing access to it as needed.

Discovery metadata within this portal are being continually improved.

NERC Data Policy

The NERC Data Policy details our commitment to support the long-term management of data.

Find out more about our Data Policy

NERC Metadata Standard

The NERC Metadata Standard is a GEMINI 2 and INSPIRE compliant standard with an environmental focus.

Find out more about our Metadata Standard V1.0

How can I find NERC's data?

The DCS allows you to search a catalogue of metadata (information describing data) to discover and gain access to NERC's data holdings and information products. The metadata are prepared to a common NERC Metadata Standard and are provided to the catalogue by the Data Centres.

What can I do and get from the DCS?

You can interrogate the catalogue in the way that best fits your needs. You can find records of interest by searching for specific words or phrases, and/or a particular time or place. You can build complex text searches, targeting specific metadata fields or search the records as a whole.

The abstracts that are displayed alongside the results of your search will allow you to identify which records to investigate further. We also indicate which records carry a link to an online resource. The full details of each record can be viewed, including any conditions that apply to access and use. You can also download a copy of the metadata record in a variety of different metadata standards.

Find out more about the DCS.

Bookmark with: Delicious Digg Facebook reddit StumbleUpon Twitter

NERC Data Catalogue Service version 1.4 ©2013
A light version of the portal is available for mobile and other limited browsers.

NERC DCS - Metadata g: Remote Sensing Data from the NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF)

http://data-search.nerc.ac.uk/search/full/catalogue/neodc.nerc.ac.uk_NERC_D...

Search for data

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Details

Title: Remote Sensing Data from the NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF)

Abstract: The Airborne Research & Survey Facility (ARSF, formerly Airborne Remote Sensing Facility) is managed by NERC Scientific Services and Programme Management. It provides the UK environmental science community, and other potential users, with the means to obtain remotely-sensed data in support of research, survey and monitoring programmes. The ARSF is a unique service providing environmental researchers, engineers and surveyors with synoptic analogue and digital imagery of high spatial and spectral resolution. The NEODC holds the entire archive of Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) and Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) data acquired by the NERC ARSF. High-resolution scanned digital versions of the entire collection of analogue photographs are now also available as well as selected LiDAR-derived elevation and terrain models for selected sites flown using the sensor.

Temporal coverage: These data span the period from to inclusive.

Resource locator: miscellaneous
CEDA Dataset Homepage

DOWNLOAD - ARSF Data Directory

Conditions for access and use constraints: Restrictions Apply

Responsible party - Distributor
NEODC
Individual name: Data Center Contact
Position: Data Center Contact
Address: NERC Earth Observation Data Centre, NEODC, Space Science and Technology Department, STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Chilton, Didcot, Oxfordshire, OX11 0QX
Email: support(at)ceda(dot)ac(dot)uk
Telephone: +44 (0)1235 778123

Full metadata details

Unique resource identifier (URI) neodc.nerc.ac.uk:NERC_DMS_0.7:dataent_11716368890815055

NERC Data Catalogue Service (DCS)

- NERC DCS search directs users to ARSF dataset at CEDA....

Viewing Remote Sensing Data from the NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF)

http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_1171636889081

Centre for Environmental Data Archival
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Search for in (Go)

Remote Sensing Data from the NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF)

General Info

Title: Remote Sensing Data from the NERC Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF)

Type: Data Entity

Sub-Type: Measurement

Abbreviation: ARSF

Publication State: published

URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_11716368890815055

Summary

The Airborne Research & Survey Facility (ARSF, formerly Airborne Remote Sensing Facility) is managed by NERC Scientific Services and Programme Management. It provides the UK environmental science community, and other potential users, with the means to obtain remotely-sensed data in support of research, survey and monitoring programmes. The ARSF is a unique service providing environmental researchers, engineers and surveyors with synoptic analogue and digital imagery of high spatial and spectral resolution. The NEODC holds the entire archive of Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) and Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) data acquired by the NERC ARSF. High-resolution scanned digital versions of the entire collection of analogue photographs are now also available as well as selected LIDAR-derived elevation and terrain models for selected sites flown using the sensor.

Content

i Introduction

The ARSF is a unique service providing environmental researchers, engineers and surveyors with synoptic analogue and digital imagery of high spatial and spectral resolution. Such a comprehensive data service cannot be easily achieved by other survey techniques.

The ARSF currently uses a Dornier 228 aircraft. This extensively modified aircraft is not only capable of accommodating the current ARSF core instrumentation, as well as additional experimental optical and geophysical sensors, but is also configured to deploy a range of atmospheric instrumentation and samplers.

The operational flying season generally spans from early March until early October. Three elements determine this period:

- weather, solar zenith angle and vegetation state
- maintenance on the aircraft
- sensor maintenance is performed by the manufacturers between November and January

Every day during this season, the ARSF has to make difficult decisions on whether or not to attempt flying based on weather forecasts, and to prioritise the most important projects based on many parameters. Flying schedule is available from the ARSF website.

The NERC Airborne Research & Survey Facility (ARSF) provides the UK's environmental science community with:

- **Aerial photography data**, using an analogue camera, the Wild RC-10 visible NIR, in conjunction with CASI and ATM instruments.
- **Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM)**. ARSF has flown two ATM instruments over the period 1982 - 2008: the Daedalus 1268 was operated from 1982 until 1998. Since 1996 and until 2008 an upgraded version - the Azimuth Systems AZ-16 was used, along with an improved data acquisition system.

NERC Data Catalogue Service (DCS)

- ...and to the CEDA tools to allow them to find exactly what they need

Background layers: (Select One)

- Demis world map
- ENVISAT MERIS mosaic

NEODC layers:

- NEXTMap Britain tiles
- ARSF ATM
- ARSF CASI
- ARSF scanned photos
- ARSF Lidar
- LANDSAT-7 ETM
- LANDSAT-4/5 TM
- ARSF sites

Environment Agency layers:

[redraw map](#)

Reference Map
(click to reposition map)

Powered by MapServer

On-line data coverage viewer at
CEDA

- Traditionally have provided http, and ftp access to data, as well as data delivery on physical media.
- Also have developed on-line interfaces for data subsetting and visualisation.
- The CEDA Web Processing Service (WPS) is the latest of these.
- Based on OGC standards
- OpenDAP also implemented for some datasets.

Submission Form for process: Subsetter - Google Chrome

CEDA OGC WEB SERVICES
Web Processing Service

Capabilities (XML) | Documentation | Admin | Contact | Disclaimer

Home | Processes | Jobs | Login

Show news | Go to news page

Define the inputs for the Subsetter process

Please complete the form below to submit a request to run the Subsetter process. Note that some processes are restricted to registered users only. Click the 'Submit' button to submit your request.

Process Abstract A Subsetting tool that allows the extraction of variable subsets from a range of datasets. The user can select a dataset, a single variable, time range and bounding box. The output format can also be selected (NetCDF or CSV) along with instructions on how to divide output files into sensible time chunks. The tool uses CDAT's CDMS (Climate Data Management System) libraries to interact with the datasets in the archives. The extraction jobs run on the batch processing servers and the user is e-mailed when the job has completed.

This process includes fields for which the possible values are dependent on other selections you have made (these are known as *dynamic fields*). The form works from top to bottom so please start by selecting an option for the first field. Once you have made your selection the form will automatically update to show the next available options in the fields below. You can instruct the form to update by clicking the 'Update form' button and you can re-set it to the initial values using the 'Reset form' button.

Update form | Reset form | Submit

Dataset Met Office Stratospheric Assimilated Data | Please select an item from the list shown.

Variable -- Dynamic field (see instructions) -- | This field is dynamic and the available options depend upon selections you have made for some, or all, of the fields above.

Start Date Time -- Dynamic field (see instructions) -- | Please insert a date/time field in the format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss such as 2009-02-01T00:00:00. This field is dynamic and the available options depend upon selections you have made for some, or all, of the fields above.

End Date Time -- Dynamic field (see instructions) -- | Please insert a date/time field in the format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss such as 2009-02-01T00:00:00. This field is dynamic and the available options depend upon selections you have made for some, or all, of the fields above.

Bounding Box Current Bounding Box: -180.0 -90.0 180.0 90.0 | Reset bounding box.

Extracted data

Centre for Environmental Data Archival

CEDA Data (Sept 2013)

Project	Type	Current archive volume (Tb)
NEODC	Earth Observation	400 (<i>was 300 in 2012</i>)
BADC	Atmospheric Science	500 (<i>was 350 in 2012</i>)
CMIP5	Climate Model	1000 (<i>was 350 in 2012</i>)
Total		1900 Tb = 1.9 Pb

Data themselves come from a wide range of sources:
Observations, Satellites, aircraft, numerical models. -> "data deluge"

Volume of data has doubled in 12 months. -> Petascale

Total storage available is 5 Pb –and all has been allocated!

Storage will increase to 11Pb over the next 2 years.

Centre for Environmental Data Archival

CEDA Users

~3000 active users

Most are from:

- Universities (71%)
- Government (18%)

Centre for Environmental Data Archival

CEDA Users

Diverse range of CEDA user disciplines

BADC Download Statistics

A ~small dataset is most popular!

Time break down

Period	Users	Methods	Datasets	Number(M)	Size(GB)	Active days
2012Q3	1103	6	157	1.806633	7701	5371
2012Q4	1076	6	144	0.110429	3481	3986
2013Q1	1141	6	161	0.326532	2530	4630
2013Q2	1255	6	147	0.165172	3786	4684
2013Q3	830	6	148	0.284748	2999	3214
ALL	3695	6	169	2.693514	20499	21885

Users by Quarter

Most popular datasets

Dataset	Users	Methods	Number	Size(MB)	Activity days
cru	1626	3	34135	1373576	3528
midas	817	3	20822	1884263	2747
cmip5	200	3	25398	4878801	904
faam	184	5	20966	268695	1657
hadisst	152	3	2211	30190	350
badc	130	5	44731	210251	408
surface	126	5	3837	744	330
nimrod	110	3	12185	267440	703
ecmwf-era-interim	101	3	64534	2827247	350
project_spaces	100	1	139794	3408444	772
radios	92	4	50337	9221	307
hadcm3	70	3	831155	318924	224
hadrm3	68	3	208062	126814	179
assim	66	3	20960	1034682	873
chilbolton	54	4	12796	27285	254
ecmwfop	53	3	29899	42567	200
era40	53	2	78259	28807	127
cet	50	2	378	16	101
um	49	3	5016	175705	150

NEODC Download Statistics

Time break down

Period	Users	Methods	Datasets	Number(M)	Size(GB)	Active days
2012Q3	93	3	28	0.109167	13270	803
2012Q4	109	3	28	0.026652	244	658
2013Q1	115	3	28	0.032789	362	702
2013Q2	112	3	27	0.072514	517	708
2013Q3	78	2	27	0.022058	389	490
ALL	333	3	32	0.26318	14784	3361

Users by Quarter

Most popular datasets

Dataset	Users	Methods	Number	Size(MB)	Activity days
arsf	74	3	7838	977898	386
msg	53	3	23699	11851	274
photo_scan	48	2	2610	80681	111
iasi	40	3	3162	2477262	270
arc	37	2	48116	164255	331
meris	32	3	118	929	102
aatsr_multimission	31	3	18125	2407465	366
nextmap	30	3	77168	119391	88
avhrr-3	22	2	1670	91364	149
neode	18	3	8402	125955	45
grape	16	3	38727	3910543	92
seviri_frp	15	3	417	2361	78
gome-2	15	3	5940	3201626	158
mtci	12	2	2521	153095	49
mipas	12	2	5640	1001820	268
sciamachy	11	1	112	0	72
casix	11	3	308	2733	115
gome	10	1	134	77	27
hirdls	10	2	16076	316751	58

- Government funding for infrastructure has enabled us to set up the JASMIN/CEMS system at CEDA
- JASMIN=“Joint Analysis System Meeting Infrastructure Needs”
- CEMS=“Centre for Environmental Monitoring from Space”
- JASMIN/CEMS are not just about supporting the traditional archival services of CEDA though – they are intended to additionally provide support for high performance analysis of high volume data by the greater NERC scientific community.
- “Bring the users *to* the data...”

JASMIN/CEMS

Science & Technology Facilities Council
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

Neighbouring buildings on the Harwell Site, Oxfordshire, UK

CEMS – what is it?

- A joint academic-industrial facility for climate and environmental data services
- Will provide:
 - Step change in EO/climate data storage, processing and analysis
 - A **scalable model** for developing services and applications : hosted in a **cloud-based infrastructure**
 - Data quality and integrity tools
 - Information on data accuracy and provenance
 - To give users confidence in the data, services and products

JASMIN/CEMS functions

CEDA data storage & services

- Curated data archive
- Archive management services
- Archive access services (HTTP, FTP, Helpdesk, ...)

Data intensive scientific computing

- Global / regional datasets & models
- High spatial, temporal resolution
- Private cloud

Flexible access to high-volume & complex data for climate & earth observation communities

- Online workspaces
- Services for sharing & collaboration

JASMIN/CEMS

- 4.6 Petabytes of “fast” disk – with excellent connectivity - to 11 Pb in next 2 years
- A compute platform for running Virtual Machines - to 3000 cores in next 2 years
- A small HPC compute cluster (known as “LOTUS”)
- Connected to :
 - Some CEMS infrastructure for commercial applications
 - JASMIN nodes at remote sites
- Dedicated network connections to specific sites

JASMIN/CEMS

- All of the CEDA archive has now been moved onto JASMIN/CEMS storage
- GWS (Group Work Spaces) and Virtual Machines are available to allow groups of users to do processing of data in the CEDA archive locally on the JASMIN system.
- Advantages :
 - ✓ No need for users to download large volumes of data to their local system.
 - ✓ No need for users to have access to their own processing capability locally.
- In the era of 'Big Data', this is increasingly important.
- Essential to provide such services to allow such large and complex datasets to be fully exploited.

CEMS Opendap

Data discovery and data download: find and access CEDA data through the CEMS interface

Home | Contact us | Links | About | Help | English

Username: Password: Login

WHAT?

WHERE?

- Any - Search

Reset Advanced Options

Applications
Audio/Video
Case studies, best practices
Conference proceedings

Show map

FIND INTERACTIVE MAPS, GIS DATASETS, SATELLITE IMAGERY AND RELATED APPLICATIONS

GEONETWORK'S PURPOSE IS:

- To improve access to and integrated use of spatial data and information
- To support decision making
- To promote multidisciplinary approaches to sustainable development
- To enhance understanding of the benefits of geographic information

GeoNetwork opensource allows to easily share geographically referenced thematic information between different organizations. For more information please contact maurizio.naqni@stfc.ac.uk

Featured map

TEMPLATE FOR VECTOR DATA IN ISO19139 (PREFERRED!)

No preview available

The ISO19115 metadata standard is the preferred metadata standard to use. If unsure what templates to start with, use this one.

Index of /mipas-oxford/data/v1.2/2002/09/

Parent directory

Filename	Download	Last modified
.checksums	2.7 KB	09/19/2011 02:28:33 AM
.summary	618 bytes	09/19/2011 02:28:33 AM
mipas_envisat_20020901_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:45 AM
mipas_envisat_20020902_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:45 AM
mipas_envisat_20020903_norm_v1.20.nc	1 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:46 AM
mipas_envisat_20020904_norm_v1.20.nc	1 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:48 AM
mipas_envisat_20020905_norm_v1.20.nc	1 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:50 AM
mipas_envisat_20020906_norm_v1.20.nc	817.5 KB	08/02/2011 10:04:50 AM
mipas_envisat_20020907_norm_v1.20.nc	1 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:51 AM
mipas_envisat_20020908_norm_v1.20.nc	551.0 KB	08/02/2011 10:04:52 AM
mipas_envisat_20020912_norm_v1.20.nc	921.2 KB	08/02/2011 10:04:53 AM
mipas_envisat_20020913_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:54 AM
mipas_envisat_20020914_norm_v1.20.nc	1 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:54 AM
mipas_envisat_20020915_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:56 AM
mipas_envisat_20020916_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:57 AM
mipas_envisat_20020917_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:04:58 AM
mipas_envisat_20020918_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:05:00 AM
mipas_envisat_20020919_norm_v1.20.nc	2 MB	08/02/2011 10:05:01 AM

JASMIN/CEMS Latest Status

- Group Workspaces provide additional capability which many projects are already finding invaluable:
- Multi-terabyte online workspace
- High-performance, parallel-IO storage can be “provisioned” rapidly in response to user needs
- GWSs are created as volumes in the same storage infrastructure as archives
- Access control -GWS manager enable secure data sharing within the group.
- Data transfer-A shared data transfer server
- Data analysis- A shared data analysis environment is available
- Dedicated virtual machines for data analysis are available on request,
- “Elastic Tape” near-line storage

JASMIN/CEMS Latest Status

- As of the time of writing (August 2013), there are:
 - 25 NCAS/JASMIN Group Workspaces,
 - total GWS allocation of 1.4 Petabytes
 - between 1 and 27 users per workspace
- JASMIN-CEMS Phase 2 underway to expand the infrastructure –funded by the NERC “Big Data” initiative.

JASMIN/CEMS Science Use cases

Example academic CEMS projects are:

- Trial processing of AATSR for Climate (ARC) Sea Surface Temperature Data (University of Edinburgh, University of Reading)
- Land Surface Temperature processing from AATSR data (University of Leicester)
- Processing/hosting GlobAlbedo data products (MSSL, UCL)
- ATSR1+2 Full Mission Reprocessing (RAL)
- Cloud Essential Climate Variables processing (RAL)

All report more efficient and faster data processing

JASMIN/CEMS Science Use case (1)

- Processing large volume EO datasets to produce:
 - Essential Climate Variables
 - Long term global climate-quality datasets e.g ESA CCI

JASMIN/CEMS Science Use Case (2)

- Cloud ECV reprocessing
- Performed by RAL Space Remote Sensing Group (RSG)
- 15 years worth of (A)ATSR data
- Co-location with JASMIN / CEMS enables combination of
 - STFC's compute cluster with
 - JASMIN / CEMS fast IO storage.

- On the previous system it took ~2-3 weeks per year of data to process the AATSR data to cloud products.
- On the JASMIN/CEMS system 3 days per year of data.
- Every 3 days cycle means reprocessing is much more feasible.
- Use of this system set-up is a 'game changer' for RSG.

JASMIN/CEMS Science Use Case (3)

LST plot for the UK [John Remedios and Darren Ghent, University of Leicester].

- “AATSR” reprocessing:
- ATSR1 and ATSR2 data reprocessed using improved algorithms into ENVISAT AATSR format data – and hence the “aatsr_multimission” archive at CEDA.
- Better algorithms means better cloud clearing and flagging, better ground calibrated and more complete coverage.
- CEDA has copies of AATSR v2.1 reprocessing done at ESA alongside the ATSR1 and 2 v2.1 data reprocessed on JASMIN
- Much easier having fast direct access to data and processing power!

JASMIN/CEMS Science Use case (4)

- User access to 5th Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5)
 - Large volumes of data from best climate models
 - Greater throughput required
 - Critical for analysis of data for next IPCC Report
- Large model data analysis facility
 - Workspaces for scientific users. Climate modellers need 100s of Tb of disk space, with high-speed connectivity
 - Large cache on fast disk available for post-processing results

JASMIN/CEMS Science Use case (5)

- “Near Real Time Ash and SO₂ Hazard Alert”
- Volcanic Gas Detection and Monitoring
- Oxford university project funded by NCAS starting Jan 2014.
- CEDA will provide NRT EUMETSAT and ECMWF data to enable early detection and monitoring of volcanic gas emissions.
- Processing software will run on the JASMIN system but be *fully managed by the Oxford group*.

Digital Object Identifiers

- CEDA is actively supporting the development and wider use of DOI's for datasets.
- DOI's mean that the dataset is CITABLE
- Users get the credit for the data they produce
- Online Data Journals now available to describe datasets

Viewing Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis UR025.3 (1989-2010) as part of the VALUE of the RAPID-WATCH Climate Change programme array (VALOR) project

The files are available as CF-compliant monthly mean netcdf files.

Documentation and Links to further information and references

M. Valdivieso and K. Haines, 2011: Scientific Validation Report (SVR) for v1 Reprocessed Analysis and Reanalysis. GMES Marine Core Services Technical Report WP04-GLO-U-Reading_v1, 28 pp, March 2011
 K. Haines, M. Valdivieso, H. Zuo and V. N. Stepanov, 2012: Transports and Budgets in a 1/4deg global ocean reanalysis 1989-2010. Ocean Sci. Discuss., 9, 261 – 290, 2012

Citation

Natural Environment Research Council, [Valdivieso M., Haines K.]. Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis UR025.3 (1989-2010) as part of the VALUE of the RAPID-WATCH Climate Change programme array (VALOR) project, [Internet]. NCS British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2013;. Date of creation. Available from http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_ACTIVITY_of1f7676-df0a-11e2-9431-00163a251233, DOI: 10.5285/aef749ed-3ee9-4ce0-a0f9-e5bb369b5861

Who to contact

Please contact the BADC with any questions or comments regarding this dataset.

Author

Name	Maria Valdivieso, Keith Haines, NCEO, Reading University	email	
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Online References

Relation	Title
Apply for access	Register as a new BADC user to download the UR025.3 data
Download	Data directory for UR025.3 data
Logo	VALOR logo

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Reading University Ocean Reanalysis Software
Activity	RAPID-WATCH - The Value of the RAPID array for climate predictions (VALOR)
Observation Station	Reading University computer

Parent Activity

No data specified at present

Sub-Activities

None

UR025.3 (1989-2010) as part of the VALUE of the RAPID-WATCH of citation. Available from :51233 , DOI: 10.5285/aef749ed-3ee9-4ce0-a0f9-e5bb369b5861

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Commentary Metadata- CHARMe

“**CHAR**acterization of **Me**tadata to enable high-quality climate applications and services”

How can climate data users decide whether a dataset is fit for their purpose?

2 Year EU project to develop the CHARMe system

CHARMe metadata

Post-fact annotations, e.g. citations, ad-hoc comments and notes;

Results of assessments, e.g. validation campaigns, intercomparisons with models or other observations, reanalysis;

Provenance, e.g. dependencies on other datasets, processing algorithms and chain, data source;

Properties of data distribution, e.g. data policy and licensing, timeliness (is the data delivered in real time?), reliability;

External events that may affect the data, e.g. volcanic eruptions, El-Nino index, satellite or instrument failure, operational changes to the orbit calculations.

General rule: information originates from **users or external entities**, not original data providers

However, sometimes information is not available from the data provider!

CEDA Summary

- Archive contains a diverse range of datasets
- CEDA supports a wide range of data users and data providers
- CEDA provides Data Management support and advice to data users, providers and policy makers
- CEDA have implemented scalable systems to deal with era of 'Big Data'
- CEDA are involved with numerous projects

Thank you!

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